

LUÍS RIBEIRO'S **FASCINATING ASTROLABE** AND NECESSARY OBSERVATIONS

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INTRODUCTION

On 31 July 2021, our colleague LUÍS CAMPOS RIBEIRO, an individual as studious and applied as BENJAMIN DYKES on the other side of the pond, Portugal, joined The Astrological Podcast of our also dear colleague CHRIS BRENNAN, author of *Hellenistic Astrology* (2017), to discuss the mathematical and/or astronomical basis of the different methods of house division. While I would have loved for more people to have seen that episode (no. 313), as it is an ideal pedagogy for any student and astrologer unfamiliar with the mechanisms behind the different house systems, I will concentrate instead on the segments where Luís conducts a measurement of **Alcabitian houses** with an **astrolabe** and that in which he explains or illustrates the **Placidus** method of house division.

It has been because of a recent dialogue with GEMINI BRETT that I have revisited this video in order to determine, as GEMINI would have wondered during our conversation, whether LUÍS touched some aspects of the Placidus method of house division I had exposed in recent days as well as in the 26 September paper (DOI [10.5281/zenodo.13841957](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13841957)). Among these, the different seasonal or ascensional times of each Placidus cuspal degree, as opposed to that of the degree occupied by the sun (upon which planetary hours will be established) or of the ASC, for whatever **seasonal times** we calculate relative to these degrees, said times will be true to those degrees only, not the rest. This is the reason for which I established a relationship between the timekeeping or seasonal method of house division (i.e. Placidus) and relativity. The reader is to be made aware of the fact that I speak not of the two forms of relativity of which we know thanks to ALBERT EINSTEIN: special (1905) and general (1915), but of the first form of relativity known to man, the «equation of time», best reflected by tropical astronomy or physics, that is, oblique ascensional times due to not velocity (special relativity) nor gravity (general relativity) as much as to the «**tilt**» of a moving frame of reference, namely, the Earth, relative to an inertial frame of reference, namely,

the ecliptic or zodiacal belt. Here is where the timekeeping or seasonal method of house division (i.e. Placidus) comes into play, known by ABRAHAM IBN EZRA as **“the method of rising times”** (trans. SHLOMO SELA)¹.

THE OBSERVATIONS

1. After having discussed all chart models (i.e. sign houses, equal-sign houses, and Porphyry) and some of the most important systems of house division (i.e. Alcabitius, Campanus, and Regiomontanus), LUÍS discusses the Placidus method (relevant part spanning from 2:30:15 to 2:38:39). LUÍS is correct when he refers to this calculation as the **hourline method**. Unfortunately, however, does not explain Placidus house cusps as much as planetary or seasonal hours, that is, the basis of the method only. LUÍS rightfully clarified (2:35:29) that they are not great circles (which alludes to trigonometry) but hourlines (which alludes to physics or primary motion), for which reason he is also correct as he states that it is very hard to work these hourlines mathematically². However, he does not seem to have made reference or employed the term «diurnal arcs», and so «ascensional or seasonal times of different oblique degrees» neither, which goes to the heart of not only the mechanism of action of this method of house division, but to that of Alcabitius — and of Koch — also (even if these abbreviate the measuring exercise in two different ways or directions).

2. Also unfortunately, I cannot speak to the reason for which LUÍS did not elaborate nor determine whether he is aware of the mechanism that takes place and makes, therefore, this uninterruptedly simultaneous or simultaneously uninterrupted calculation possible (most are not). However, I did hear him say (2:34:27) that each Placidus house measures **“two hours”** and repeats this statement seconds later (2:34:38). Of course, he could have always meant two seasonal hours (in which case one would still need clarify too that

¹ *Abraham Ibn Ezra on Nativities and Continuous Horoscopy. A Parallel Hebrew-English Critical Edition of the Book of Nativities and the Book of Revolution*. Abraham Ibn Ezra’s Astrological Writings, Volume 4. Edited, translated, and annotated by Shlomo Sela. 2014, BRILL, pp. 377, 404, 406.

² This is what Giovanni Antonio Magini (*Tabulae primi mobilis*, 1604) and Placidus de Titis (*Primum Mobile*, 1657) did as they presented their tables, which constitutes an approximation only, also referred as the method’s “makeshift” by British astrologer Michael Wackford (see “The Polar Arcs”, *Correlation*, 2001, and “Placido and the Semi-Arc Method of House Division”, *Correlation*, 1994, both made available online by Skyscript. See the references section in this document).

these two seasonal hours correspond to that cuspal degree only of which he speaks, 05° Taurus³). Approximately forty five minutes later in the podcast, however, LUÍS explained how to measure or calculate **Alcabitius houses with an astrolabe** (3:14:10–3:18:00 segment). Although he did point out that the plate of the astrolabe employed would have been designed for Lisbon (Portugal), again speaks of two hours when conducting the measurement failing to disclose a fundamental component to the viewer (perhaps involuntarily so). The two hours of which he speaks are not two normal or coordinate hours in Lisbon, but two **seasonal** hours of **said** — ascending — degree (as he is explaining the calculation under an Alcabitius conception).

3. Therefore, a hundred and twenty minutes before the time of birth (before 05° appeared at or on the horizon), **25° Gemini** would not have appeared as IC (so as to assign it to the 3rd House cusp), nor 240 minutes before the time of birth (before 05° Taurus appeared as the ASC) would have **01° Gemini** (so as to assign it to the 2nd House cusp). Our measurements with the astrolabe speak of two seasonal hours of whatever degree we select. Put simply: because its language is **astrolabian** (i.e. solar/seasonal), it does not specify the actual amount of — coordinate — time it takes for said displacement to take place.

³ For the sun displaces itself at a different ‘speed’ in each degree, that is, each day. In other words, remains a slightly different amount of time *above* and *below* the horizon *each* day, and all degrees preserve the sun’s behaviour in spite of it no longer occupying them. The tropical Zodiac was designed upon the behaviour of the sun. The properties of each segment of the ecliptic (i.e. month) bear too its footprints. These properties are a combination of solar and planetary energy or ‘radiation’. However, all become ‘regulated’ or ‘controlled’ by the sun.

4. In order to prove this, we may erect a Placidus chart for, say, 28 March 2021, 07:40:20 (local time), Lisbon, Portugal, which reflects the ascending degree used by LUÍS as an example, which is 05° Taurus:

Should we go back in time “two hours,” we would have seen that LUÍS assertions (which degree now appears as the IC) are **not** corroborated, that is, we would have found that

two hours earlier (5:40:20) would have yielded different results from the ones illustrated in the video (3:14:10–3:18:00 segment):

It would not have been the case even if we had gone back in time under an Alcabitus measurement of the houses⁴:

⁴ Almost all, if not all methods of house division respect the seasonal or ascensional time of the degrees that constitute the four angles of a — nonpolar — chart.

While LUÍS shows us that 25° Gemini would have appeared at the IC (so as to assign said degree to the 3rd House cusp), Placidus- and Alcabitius- measured houses shows us 22° 29' of that sign instead.

5. LUÍS results are corroborated only when we take into consideration the seasonal characterisation of the matter, that is, when we understand that (a) these two **nocturnal**

hours are seasonal or solar and that **(b)** they correspond to 05° Taurus only⁵. Because 05° Taurus displaces itself below the horizon at a **105 min-rate** (two seasonal hours of that degree)⁶, it is by going back in seasonal time that we are able to corroborate LUÍS assertions. 105 minutes (1 hr 45 min) earlier (5:55:20), then, we have 25° of Gemini at the IC and can therefore be assigned to the 3rd House cusp. Another two seasonal hours of *that same degree* earlier, that is, another 105 minutes earlier, 01° of Gemini would have appeared at the IC, and can therefore be assigned to the 2nd House cusp. Unlike Placidus, of course, we would be assigning these cuspal degrees, and the houses they constitute, therefore, a fictional amount of time, for it is the amount of time of 05° Taurus⁷, not of whatever two degrees would have made their way there at the time of birth⁸.

6. We may also say that these seasonal hours of 05° Taurus are to be measured both for the horizon *above* and for the horizon *below*, for the amount of time of *culmination* of this degree (05° Taurus) varies relative to its amount of time of *rise*, that is, the amount of time it takes for it to travel from the imum coeli to the local horizon, as opposed to from the horizon to the midheaven (“reach”, as GEMINI BRETT likes to call it). However, as LUÍS rightfully pointed out (3:17:16 of the video), because conducting the measurement above the horizon with this plate is quite complicated, he recommends continuing to conduct the measurement of time *below*, not above, the horizon. Therefore, for the purposes of the second exercise we are to abandon the ascending

⁵ The astrolabe seems to be designed to reflect two seasonal hours of *any* degree we select. That is, it is a Placidian (i.e. timekeeping) astrolabe; therefore, also a Koch or an Alcabitius astrolabe.

⁶ That is, it will appear at each subsequent house cusp (below the horizon) every 105 minutes before the time of birth or every 105 minutes after it sets at any time of the year, for that is the rate at which the sun moves or displaces when it occupies said point of the ecliptic at said latitude.

⁷ A Koch measurement would do **exactly** the same, although it would employ the culminating degree of the time of birth instead, not the ascending one. In either case, of course, the measurement would need be conducted both from the IC to the ASC and from the ASC to the MC (unless one has an adequate astrolabe available). The difference is that, whereas Koch would have gone *back* in time for two different quadrants, Alcabitius would have for one only, as it would have gone *forward* first. Another way to see these two measurements is as follows: Koch determines how the MC degree arrived there in the first place, and later how it would have arrived at the ASC, whereas Alcabitius determines how it will culminate (MC), then how it would have become the ASC.

⁸ The seasonal method, Placidus, would have reflected whatever two degrees would have completed one and two thirds, respectively, of their journey from the IC to the ASC.

degree momentarily so that we can focus or turn our attention to the opposite degree, that of Scorpio. Why? Because (a) we are looking to make out the (Alcabitius) house cusps of the second and fourth quadrants (after having determined those of the first and of the third) and (b) we know that anywhere on Earth, *any one degree's time above the horizon is the opposite degree's time below the horizon*. In other words, LUÍS measures the ascension of 05° Taurus through or by the descension of 05° Scorpio (an astrolabe is beautiful, yes), but, again, **misses** the above, which goes to the heart of the mechanism of action “embedded” in this fascinating astrolabe⁹.

7. If we were to elaborate on the mechanism then, we would say that, in the example presented by LUÍS, **05° Taurus** moves or displaces *below* the horizon at a rate of **105 minutes**, that is, one house cusp per 1 hr and 45 min, for this is the rate at which the opposite degree, **05° Scorpio**, displaced itself *above* the horizon. That is, 105 minutes constitutes two *nocturnal seasonal hours* ($52,5 \times 2 = 105$) of that degree of Taurus, for they constitute two *diurnal seasonal hours* of the same degree of the opposite sign, Scorpio. Therefore, the two *nocturnal* seasonal hours of **05° Scorpio** ($67,5 \times 2 = 135$) constitute or equals the two *diurnal* seasonal hours ($67,5 \times 2 = 135$) of **05° Taurus**, which allows for conducting the second exercise LUÍS masterfully illustrated. As we put 25° Scorpio in the 6th, 5th, 4th, 3rd, and 2nd House cusps, we see 05° Taurus move at the same rhythm (135 minutes or 2 hr 15 min) above the horizon, that is, appear simultaneously at the 12th, 11th, 10th, 9th, and 8th House cusps, respectively.

8. I have found that failing to disclose the above information has helped leading practitioners to believe either **(i)** that Placidus houses cannot be measured via an astrolabe, **(ii)** that Placidus houses measure or present the same time size (as LUÍS would have implied in points 2:34:27 and 2:34:38 of the video), **(iii)** and/or that only when we put the sun at a Placidian cuspal degree can we corroborate the rhythm of planetary, seasonal, or solar hours (we can corroborate this constant phenomenon, seasonal hours, by selecting any one degree above or below the horizon in any Placidus-measured chart, as demonstrated [here](#)). This is the reason for which we always must take care to clarify the following: no, in a Placidus chart, the ascending degree will appear **not** exactly two

⁹ In order to be able to visualise this mechanism entirely, you may consult our previous publication, “Illustration of the Placidian Mechanism of Action”, published 13 December 2024 at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14452568>.

seasonal hours (of that day) later (only the degree occupied by the sun would), but exactly two seasonal hours of **that** cuspal degree chosen later, for each cuspal degree represents its own ascensional time (see «proper time» in this [video](#)), that is, the ascensional time of the sun when it occupied that degree at that latitude (be this close to the equator or as far as the polar regions, where some would either never rise or rise for a brief moment, for the sun either never did or did for a brief moment). A Placidian house, then, measures not the same as the rest within the quadrant (this is the case in the Alcabitius and in the Koch measurements of the houses only). Each house constitutes a trisection, yes, but of a different ascensional time (i.e. that of that cuspal degree, not of the Asc, as in Alcabitius, nor of the MC, as in Koch). They all have relative times (or fixed relative times¹⁰) and, therefore, their sizes vary from house to house above the horizon. Only diametrically opposite houses (i.e. degrees) can have the same amount of time or spacetime size (even measure as little as a few minutes at extreme latitudes). Because this measurement is only looking to take note of the behaviour of the sky or of that of the sun relative to Earth at all times (every day of the year) and latitudes (every place), it therefore respects the very basis of tropical astrology the most faithfully by accounting perfectly for movement or displacement in the spacetime dimension. This is the reason for which it is the only method naturally compatible or a hundred percent equivalent with seasonal hours (otherwise known, perhaps confusingly so, as planetary hours).

9. Because the hourlines of an astrolabe correspond to two seasonal hours of whatever degree we placed at the horizon with our — Placidian (primary motion) — plate designed for that latitude on Earth, its language is relative, therefore (see: equation of time). That an astrolabe can be employed to calculate Alcabitius houses indicates that Placidus houses can too, be calculated with said instrument, for Alcabitius — and Koch — are children of Placidus, and speaks to the *naturalism* inherent in all three (despite the first two being an abbreviation of the measuring exercise), as opposed to the popular belief according to which only a software or complex mathematics can calculate Placidus houses. **Let us prove it now.**

¹⁰ Whatever amount of time 05° Taurus would have invested in culminating in Lisbon, it is the same amount of time it will always invest in culminating in that latitude without regard to the position of the sun throughout the ecliptic, that is, regardless of the time of year. The same is applicable to all degrees; their — relative — times are *fixed* at each latitude.

THE FASCINATING TRUTH

10. Despite the masterful illustration made by our colleague, we will show now something not only interesting but also incredibly unnecessary, however: the — Alcabitian — exercise LUÍS conducted, for whatever zodiacal degree he places on or at the horizon line, this astrolabe would have **already provided** the intermediate — natural (i.e. Placidus) — house cusps¹¹. As he conducts an Alcabitius measurement with said instrument, he only verifies or corroborates both the natural integrity and the theoretical strength of the Placidus method of house division. In other words, it is primary motion (i.e. timekeeping, rising times, proper times, seasonal times) that allows or makes his exercise even possible in the first place¹², for the astrolabe was designed accordingly (i.e. in accordance with primary motion).

¹¹ Like sundials, it would simply reflect or measure the sky exactly as any living organism would see it before it, be it animal, plant, or humanoid.

¹² If the Alcabitius method — as well as Koch — derive from or are children of Placidus in the sense that, while Placidus complies with a complete measurement, they abbreviate it, it follows that only a complete measurement (Placidus) would reflect the true — temporal — **distance** of a celestial object (be it a point of the ecliptic or a planet) from an angle, an argument (i.e. angularity) shamefully employed by some to justify the measurement of Alcabitius. We say ‘shamefully’ because not only do most, if not all quadrant house systems measure or reflect the four angular cusps correctly but because it is — or should be consider to be — a truism. Take any relatively extreme latitude to verify this assertion by comparing the same astrograph under two different time-based measurements, Placidus and Alcabitius (or Koch). Better arguments need be employed, therefore. Another argument particularly absurd has been to say that “*intermediate cusps* must accurately reflect the motion of the planets *at the time of the nativity.*” First, only a natural (i.e. seasonal) measurement of the sky (i.e. Placidus) can reflect the actual intermediate cusps of the local sky. Second, Alcabitius does not trisect the quadrants in accordance with the time of culmination of the degree occupied by the sun “at the time of the nativity,” but with that of the ascending degree (not necessarily occupied by said star). In other words, Alcabitius measures the time of a different day from that of the day of birth (unless the degree occupied by the sun at the time of birth coincides with the time at which said degree crossed or rose above the horizon). Even if one were to say that said solar degree is universal, for which reason one would measure “the angularity” of the local ascending degree in its stead, one would still not reflect the **true** — temporal — distance of any object within the quadrant from either of the two angles, for the zodiacal degrees within the quadrant (their amounts of time, that is) have been measured inaccurately. In other words, Alcabitius may indicate that a certain amount of time has elapsed since said object (which occupies a point of the ecliptic, i.e. zodiacal degree) rose, when it has actually elapsed a **different** amount of time.

11. Let the viewer pause the video at any moment during LUÍS' rotation of the rete and **compare** the cuspal degrees appearing *at each two seasonal hourlines of that astrolabe* **with** the cuspal degrees your software reveals for said (Placidus) cusps in Lisbon. You may use the date provided earlier. Now please make your software show these cusps under an Alcabitius measurement of the chart. You will have unequivocally found that the house cusps of LUÍS' astrolabe are those of Placidus (accurate measurement of seasonal times), not Alcabitius (abbreviated or approximated measurement of seasonal times).

12. I have paused the video when what would seem to be the 10° of Pisces appear exactly at the horizon line (a few minutes after said degree, if you were to look very closely), for which reason same point of the opposite degree, Virgo, appears exactly at the opposite end of that hourline, in which case would make it **05:26:09** of the same date (28 March 2021). Let us now take care to see which degrees this Lisbon astrolabe reveals at the rest of the hourlines, in which case they would constitute the house cusps below the horizon (thereby necessarily providing those above). The 2nd House cusp would appear to be 25° Aries, whereas the 3rd, the 4th, the 5th, and the 6th would appear to be 26° Taurus, 19° Gemini, 10° Cancer, and 05° Leo, respectively. Now turn to your software and compare the results. Are not these degrees in your software the same as

the ones shown by LUÍS' astrolabe? Indeed!¹³ Should the reader not feel secure still, pause the video now at 03:16:05, when LUÍS puts the horizon hourline of his astrolabe only a few minutes past 12° Aquarius (in which case you should enter the time of 04:09:20 in your software) and make the comparison once again. Are they not the same Placidian cusps your software shows? Certainly.

As both MICHAEL WACKFORD and ROBERT POWELL rightfully state in their “Placido and the Semi-Arc Method” (1994, *Correlation*) and *History of the Houses* (1996, ACS Publications), respectively, Placidus was known or referred to as the **“astrolabe method”** by ABRAHAM IBN EZRA, who, again, according to 2014's SHLOMO SELA's English translation (Brill), EZRA also described it as “the method of rising times” (pp. 377, 404, 406), which is very similar, if not the same, as “the method of *proper* times”¹⁴.

The Woodlands, TX
23 December 2024

¹³ Please continue to pause the video at different times during the rotation of the rete and confirm yet again the mechanical integrity of Luís' astrolabe (or the algorithmic or mathematical one of your software).

¹⁴ As we have suggested in recent publications, following the definition of the term under relativity theory, which is not as close to the word “appropriate” as it is to the word “one's own” time (i.e. the time of *that* specific degree or of the sun when it occupied *it* at a *that* latitude).

APPENDIX

SEASONAL OR ASCENSIONAL TIMES OF ALL CUSPAL DEGREES (38°N)

Example of Lisbon, Portugal

28 March 2021 | 07:40:19

Measurement	Ec. point	ST 12/24	2 SH = 1/6	Ec. point	Measurement
<i>above the horizon</i>	<i>above the horizon</i>	<i>above/below the horizon</i>	<i>above/below the horizon</i>	<i>below the horizon</i>	<i>below the horizon</i>
ASC degree	05° 00'	13 h 24 min 24 s	134 min 4 s	05° 00'	DES degree
12 th cusp	18° 32'	11 h 28 min 48 s	114 min 48 s	18° 32'	6 th cusp
11 th cusp	14° 53'	10 h 9 min 12 s	101 min 32 s	14° 53'	5 th cusp
10 th cusp	20° 14'	9 h 27 min 48 s	94 min 38 s	20° 14'	4 th cusp
9 th cusp	28° 46'	9 h 15 min 30 s	92 min 35 s	28° 46'	3 rd cusp
8 th cusp	05° 55'	9 h 32 min 48 s	95 min 28 s	05° 55'	2 nd cusp

05° Taurus 00'	rises at	7:40:19	28 March
18° Pisces 32'	rose <i>above</i> the horizon at	05:45:30	28 March
14° Aquarius 53'	rose <i>above</i> the horizon at	04:17:10	28 March
20° Capricorn 14'	rose <i>above</i> the horizon at	02:56:19	28 March
28° Sagittarius 46'	rose <i>above</i> the horizon at	01:29:42	28 March
05° Sagittarius 55'	rose <i>above</i> the horizon at	23:42:59	27 March

05° Scorpio 00'	rests at	7:40:19	28 March
18° Virgo 32'	rested <i>below</i> the horizon at	05:45:30	28 March
14° Leo 53'	rested <i>below</i> the horizon at	04:17:10	28 March
20° Cancer 14'	rested <i>below</i> the horizon at	02:56:19	28 March
28° Gemini 46'	rested <i>below</i> the horizon at	01:29:42	28 March
05° Gemini 55'	rested <i>below</i> the horizon at	23:42:59	27 March

Times spent above or below the horizon remain the same at said latitude regardless of the time of year.

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